

KHSO₄ assisted Michael addition-elimination reactions of formylated acetophenones in water : A facile general green synthetic route to 3-(alkyl/aralkyl/aryl)amino-1-arylprop-2-en-1-ones

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Abstract : A facile general green synthetic route to 3-(alkyl/aralkyl/aryl)amino-1-arylprop-2-en-1-ones in excellent yields has been developed by reacting formylated acetophenones with primary amines assisted by KHSO₄ in water.

Keywords : Michael addition, formylation, enamines, elimination, acetophenones.

Introduction

Water plays an essential role in life processes, however, its use as a solvent has been limited in organic synthesis. Despite the fact that it is the cheapest, safest and most non-toxic solvent in the world, its presence is generally avoided through the dehydrative drying of substrates and solvents. The use of water as a medium for organic reactions is, therefore, one of the latest challenges for modern organic chemists. A large number of reports on the use of water as solvent for organic reactions have appeared in the recent past¹⁻¹⁴. Michael addition to electron deficient olefins are promoted by several Lewis acids such as, Yb(OTf)₃.3H₂O¹⁵, zirconium triflate¹⁶, samarium triiodide¹⁷ and CeCl₃.7H₂O-NaI¹⁸. Catalytic asymmetric Lewis acid mediated Michael addition reactions have been reported^{19,20}. However, majority of Lewis acids cannot play their desired role in water because of the basic character of water molecules. Recently, aluminiumdodecylsulphate²¹ and KHSO₄^{22,23} have been shown to substitute for Lewis acids in water. Keeping in view the synthetic importance enamines **3**, we recently reported²⁴ a facile novel synthetic route to molecules of this class and have demonstrated their synthetic potentials^{25,26}. In our previous report²⁵ we have shown that the formylated acetophenones **2** reacted with aromatic amines in acetic acid at room temperature giving

the desired enamines in excellent yields. However, this reaction did not take place either in refluxing ethanol or under MW irradiation. It is probably due to poor nucleophilic character of the aromatic amines. On the other hand, when the reaction was carried out with alkyl or aralkylamines, which are better nucleophiles, in refluxing ethanol or under MW irradiation, the desired products were obtained in good to excellent yields. However, this reaction failed in acetic acid. This failure could be attributed to the reduced nucleophilic character of the comparatively stronger bases (alkyl or aralkylamines) due to protonation in acetic acid. Thus, this efficient method failed to be a general synthetic strategy for enamines derived from acetophenones. We now report, a general, efficient and green approach to molecules of this class assisted by KHSO₄ in water (Scheme 1).

Results and discussion

Thus, when an equimolar mixture of **2** and primary amine in water containing KHSO₄ was stirred at 50 °C, work up of the reaction mixture yielded the desired products **3** in excellent yields. The reaction was found to be equally facile with alkyl, aralkyl and aryl amines. The products were obtained in almost quantitative yields. The structures of the products were established with the help of spectral and analytical data and also by comparing

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

Table 1. Preparation of 3-(alkyl/aralkyl/aryl)amino-1-arylprop-2-en-1-ones (3a-s)

Compd.	Ar	R	Reaction time (h)	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)/lit. ²⁵ (m.p.)
3a	C ₆ H ₅	Me	3	83	132-133/130-131
3b	4-MeC ₆ H ₄	Me	3.5	80	115/115-116
3c	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	Me	2.5	92	100/99-100
3d	C ₆ H ₅	Et	2.5	89	Gum
3e	4-MeC ₆ H ₄	Et	3	90	84-85
3f	4-MeOC ₆ H ₄	Et	2	87	75-76
3g	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂	5	96	80-81/81
3h	4-MeOC ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂	6	95	65/65-66
3i	4-MeC ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂	6	93	111/112-113
3j	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	1.5	86	140-141/141-142
3k	C ₆ H ₅	4-MeC ₆ H ₄	2	91	157-158/157-159
3l	C ₆ H ₅	4-MeOC ₆ H ₄	1	94	148-149/147-148
3m	C ₆ H ₅	4-BrC ₆ H ₄	1.5	90	177-178/177
3n	4-MeC ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅	1	98	162-163/161-162
3o	4-MeC ₆ H ₄	4-MeC ₆ H ₄	2	96	186/185-186
3p	4-MeOC ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅	1	91	159/159-160
3q	4-MeOC ₆ H ₄	4-MeC ₆ H ₄	1	95	152-153/151-152
3r	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	4-MeC ₆ H ₄	2	94	201-202/202-203
3s	3-MeOC ₆ H ₄	4-MeOC ₆ H ₄	1	88	121/121-122

with those already reported. A plausible mechanism for the formation of these products has been rationalized herein. Initial protonation of oxygen atom of **2** in the presence of the acid facilitates attack by the nitrogen atom of amine at the β -carbon giving the enol, which subsequently reverts to the keto form with the elimination of the dimethylamino group from the β -carbon leading to the desired enaminone **3** (Scheme 2).

Experimental

Melting points were recorded by open capillary method and are uncorrected. The infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 983 spectrometer. High resolution ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR (300 MHz) spectra were recorded on Bruker ACF-300 spectrometer. The chemical shifts (δ ppm) and the coupling constants (Hz) are reported in the

standard fashion with reference to TMS as internal reference. FAB-mass spectra (MS) were measured on JEOL 3SX 102/DA-6000 mass spectrometer using argon as the FAB gas and *m*-nitrobenzylalcohol as the matrix. Elemental analyses were performed on a Vario-EL III instrument. Formylated acetophenones **2** were synthesized by our previously reported procedure²⁷.

3-(Alkyl/aralkyl/aryl)amino-1-arylprop-2-en-1-ones (3a-s): *General procedure*: To a mixture of **2** (1 mmol) and amine (1 mmol) in water 4 mL, KHSO₄ (2 mmol) was added and the resulting mixture was stirred at 50 °C for 1–6 h. On completion of the reaction (monitored by tlc), the product was extracted with dichloromethane (2 × 2 mL). The combined organic extract was washed with water (2 × 3 mL), dried (Na₂SO₄) and the solvent distilled to give a viscous mass, which on trituration with hexane yielded practically pure product in 83–98% yields. Further purification of the products **3a-c** and **3e-i** was achieved by crystallization from hexane-ether and of **3j-s** from methanol. **3d** was purified by column chromatography (silica gel, 10% EtOAc-hexane). In case of reactions with methylamine and ethylamine, three equivalents of the amines were used. Spectral data of unknown products **3d-f** and of **3g** and **3j** are given below:

3-Ethylamino-1-phenylprop-2-en-1-one (3d): IR (KBr): 1598, 1634, 3285 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃): δ 1.28 (3H, t, *J* 7.6 Hz), 3.30–3.37 (2H, m), 5.69 (1H, d, *J* 7.6 Hz), 6.98 (1H, dd, *J* 7.6, 5.2 Hz), 7.39–7.44 (3H, m), 7.86–7.88 (2H, m), 10.34 (1H, broad m); MS: *m/z* 176 (MH⁺) (Found: C, 75.65; H, 7.44; N, 7.90. Calcd. for C₁₁H₁₃NO (175.23): C, 75.40; H, 7.48; N, 7.99%).

3-Ethylamino-1-(4-methylphenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (3e): IR (KBr): 1609, 1636, 3431 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃): δ 1.27 (3H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz), 2.38 (3H, s), 3.30–3.34 (2H, m), 5.68 (1H, d, *J* 7.6 Hz), 6.95 (1H, dd, *J* 7.6, 5.2 Hz), 7.21 (2H, d, *J* 8 Hz), 7.78 (2H, d, *J* 8 Hz), 10.30 (1H, broad m); MS: *m/z* 190 (MH⁺) (Found: C, 76.01; H, 8.02; N, 7.50. Calcd. for C₁₂H₁₅NO (189.25): C, 76.16; H, 7.99; N, 7.40%).

3-Ethylamino-1-(4-methoxyphenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (3f): IR (KBr): 1603, 1628, 3430 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃): δ 1.27 (3H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz), 3.12–3.33 (2H, m), 3.85 (3H, s), 5.65 (1H, d, *J* 7.6 Hz), 6.90–6.96 (3H, m), 7.86 (2H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz), 10.24 (1H, broad m); MS: *m/z* 206 (MH⁺)

(Found: C, 70.41; H, 7.35; N, 6.71. Calcd. for C₁₂H₁₅NO₂ (205.25): C, 70.22; H, 7.37; N, 6.82%).

3-Benzylamino-1-phenylprop-2-en-1-one (3g): IR (KBr): 1585, 1633, 3265 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃): δ 4.47 (2H, d, *J* 6.0 Hz), 5.78 (1H, d, *J* 7.6 Hz), 7.03 (1H, dd, *J* 7.6, 5.2 Hz), 7.23–7.52 (8H, m), 7.87–7.89 (2H, m), 10.61 (1H, broad m); MS: *m/z* 238 (MH⁺).

3-Anilino-1-phenylprop-2-en-1-one (3j): IR (KBr): 1595, 1631, 3435 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃): δ 6.03 (1H, d, *J* 7.6 Hz), 7.07–7.56 (9H, m), 7.93–7.95 (2H, m), 12.15 (1H, broad m); MS: *m/z* 224 (MH⁺).

Conclusion:

To conclude, we have developed a facile general green synthetic route to enamines, a potent class of synthons, derived from commercially available acetophenones. The importance of the protocol lies in its generality, easy reaction procedure and work-up, short reaction time, high yields with high degree of purity and eco-friendliness (water as reaction medium).

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